

A LEVEL SET METHOD FOR VACUUM INFUSION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The present paper examines the fabric compaction phenomena occurring during fluid infusion in VARI (vacuum infusion) as a consequence of the stress transfer between the infused fluid and the fabric preform. This stress transfer mechanisms leads to a significant thickness change during processing. The panel thickness evolution during the process was measured using the three dimensional digital image correlation technique in a set of detailed vacuum infusion experiments using corn syrup blends as the viscous fluid infiltrated through an E-glass plain weave preform. The evolution of the displacement field of the vacuum bag surface is measured with this technique during the filling and post-filling stages. A model was developed to study the pressure and compaction displacement field evolution during the propagation of the fluid through the porous fabric preform. The model is based on the resolution of the Darcy's equation for incompressible fluids using the level set approach and accounting also for the deformation of the fabric preform. The parameters of the model, permeability, fiber bed compaction law and viscosity of the fluid are measured independently and used as input data for the model. The results of the model are compared in terms of thickness and pressure evolution through the fiber preform.

1 INTRODUCTION

VARI (vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding or vacuum infusion) is an open mould process with reduced tooling costs in comparison with the standard resin transfer moulding techniques (RTM). The procedure is based on the use of the vacuum driving force to infiltrate resin through a bagged fiber preform. The fact that one of the mould faces is replaced by a vacuum bag make this process complex to control from the viewpoint of the final thickness and, especially, from the void content of the composite part. During the last years, special efforts were made to understand the physical mechanisms involved in the infiltration process including flow, compaction and curing with the aim of developing efficient constitutive equations for accurate and predictive simulation tools (see for instance Advani and coworkers relevant literature in this field in Correia *et al.* [1], Šimáček *et al.* [2], Šimáček *et al.* [3]). The compaction phenomena occurring during infusion process is a consequence of the stress interaction between the infused resin and the fiber bed preform. At the beginning of the process, the fiber preform is vacuum bagged and the atmospheric pressure transferred directly to the fiber bed skeleton. When the resin is infused, a stress transfer between the fluid and the fiber bed is produced resulting in a spring-back effect in the fiber preform with the corresponding increase of its initial thickness. The part thickness evolves monotonically until the saturation of the composite part is attained after the steady-state regime is completed. The pressure field in vacuum infusion process is, therefore, a result of the local compaction phenomena which modifies the permeability of the fiber bed and influences the final infusion driving force. As a result, the pressure field in vacuum infusion is not longer linear within the infused length as in standard resin transfer moulding where the constant cavity thickness prevent the pressure induced permeability variation during the preform injection. Relevant models developed up-to-the-date (see an extensive review in Correia *et al.* [1]) for the analysis of the

resin infusion process are derived from the simultaneous application of the Terzaghi's effective stress theory and the Darcy's and continuity equation for the fluid flow. The fabric compressibility introduces additional difficulties with respect to the constant thickness case (RTM) which are taken into account directly by formulating the continuity equation in the deformed control volume of the material. This analysis give rise to a non-linear partial differential equation for the pressure field which can be solved with the appropriate boundary and initial conditions imposed at the inlet and outlet resin gates. The final pressure field is essentially controlled by the permeability and compressibility of the fiber bed which varies with the fiber volume fraction according to the local pressure transfer mechanism.

In this work, we have set-up a level set approach for the analysis of fluid flow and fabric compaction during resin infusion in composite materials. For simplicity, the model was applied to the one-dimensional in-plane flow through a porous fiber preform (standard VARI without distribution media) with a moving boundary (flow front) although the technique can be extended easily to multidimensional flow. From the experimental viewpoint, infusion tests were carried out in a highly controlled environment and the compaction displacements were obtained through digital image correlation during the filling and post-filling phases. A set of two cameras were used to acquire images of the bagged surface of the infusion experiment at specific times and using them to determine the compaction displacement evolution of the fiber preform, Figure 1. All the physical properties used in the model, permeability, viscosity, fiber bed compaction, were determined from independent tests. The level set method was used to track the fluid front and the results compared with the experiments in terms of vacuum bag compaction displacements and resin pressure evolution.

Figure 1: b) Experimental set-up of the infusion experiments using DIC for bag displacement measurements.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Vacuum infusion experiments were carried-out to study the compaction phenomena occurring during the infusion of a fluid through an E-glass plain woven fabric [4]. Fabric strips of $L=250\text{mm}$ and $B=80\text{mm}$ were first cut and then placed on an PMMA tool surface previously coated with a release agent using a $[0]_8$ and $[0]_4$ lay-up configurations. The fiber preform was covered a standard vacuum bag ($5\mu\text{m}$ NBF-540-LFT) and the whole set sealed with standard tacky tape (LTT-90B). Resin inlet and outlet were connected to a 12mm diameter rigid tube to the fluid pot and vacuum pump, respectively. blend of corn syrup with water at a typical concentration of $\approx 70\% \approx 30\%$ was used as infusion fluid in the experiments. The corn syrup blends were first degassed for 20 minutes using a vacuum container immediately before the experiments took place. The pressure gradient through the flow propagation direction was monitored with three pressure transducers (Omega PX61V0-100AV) equally distributed over the length of the infusion strip at 25, 50 and 75% of its length. The transducers were inserted in the mould through specific cylindrical cavities machined on it. The outlet vacuum was

controlled by a screw-driven valve regulator (TESCOM DV) while a pressure transducer (HBM P8AP) was used to monitor the current vacuum pump pressure applied in each of the experiments. The displacement field due to fabric compaction (thickness variation), $\Delta h(x,t)$, was obtained by means of the digital image correlation technique, DIC3D (from Correlated Solutions Inc.). To this end, the vacuum side of the experiment was first sprayed with white paint followed by the dispersion of black dots to create the speckle required for the displacement correlation. Two digital cameras were placed close to the experiments as appears in Figure 1. High resolution images (29Mpx) were acquired by the two digital cameras at a rate of 1 image per six seconds. The digital image correlation was performed only over an specific area of interest (AOI) of $L_{AOI}=0.21m$ and $B_{AOI}=0.01m$. The individual particle position is tracked by the system over the area of interest (AOI) in the test and this information is used to obtain the three dimensional displacement field in the vacuum side.

As soon as the fluid enters into the bag, a slight decrease of the local thickness is produced which is usually attributed to fluid lubrication effects at the flow front position. Afterwards, a monotonic increase of the thickness is observed and this phenomenon is associated with the a stress transfer mechanisms between the fiber bed and the infusion fluid. The external load initially supported by the fiber bed skeleton is now transferred to the fluid pressure producing a spring-back effect with the subsequent increase of the fabric thickness which is detected in detail by the digital image correlation system, Figure 2.

Figure 2. Displacement field $\Delta h(x, t)$ within the AOI for the different infusion times.

The full displacement compaction displacement within the AOI is also showed in Figure 2 for different infusion times. Very interestingly, the digital image correlation system is able to capture the plain woven fabric roughness and small vacuum bag profile undulations around the mid-line are clearly observed. The displacement profile time evolution is monotonic until the fluid front reaches the outlet gate and the total saturation of the fabric is produced being the larger displacement observed at the inlet gate of the infusion experiment.

3 MODEL

The model used in this work is based on the resolution of the Darcy's equations for the fluid flow through porous media. Darcy's equation establish a linear relation between the average fluid velocity through the fiber preform and the externally imposed pressure gradient, being the proportionality factor related with the fabric permeability tensor \mathbf{K} and the fluid viscosity μ . By combining the Darcy's and continuity equation for compacting bag, the following differential equation for the pressure field $p(x,t)$ can be obtained [1-3]

$$\nabla\left(\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \cdot \nabla p\right) = \frac{-1}{V_f} \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where V_f is the fiber volume fraction of the reinforcement. The stress transfer between the fiber bed p_{fiber} and the infusion fluid p is established by means of the Terzaghi's effective stress theory as $p_{\text{atm}} = p_{\text{fiber}} + p$. The permeability tensor as well as the fiber volume fraction depends on the fiber pressure leading to a non-linear differential equation. The resolution of the partial derivative equation requires, previously, the knowledge of the physical parameters involved in the infusion process, namely, fiber bed compressibility $V_f(p_{\text{fiber}})$, permeability $K(V_f)$ and fluid viscosity μ . Those parameters were determined experimentally by a set of independent experimental tests [4].

This general governing equation for the pressure field $p(x,t)$ is valid when the fluid fills completely the solution domain. However, when dealing with the flow evolution through the fiber preform a numerical strategy should be set-up to account for the flow evolution. In this paper, a level set method is implemented based on the mathematical developments carried by Osher and Sethian [5]. The flow front is defined with the aid of a function $\phi(x,t)$ understood as the zero level curve of a higher order function defined as $\phi(x(t),t) = 0$. Therefore, tracking the fluid interface problem is equivalent to find the zero level of the evolving function ϕ during the fluid propagation. Taking the differential of the former expression and using the chain rule, the initial value problem for the level set function can be obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + F |\nabla \phi| = 0 \quad (2)$$

where F is the velocity normal to the fluid front (tangential velocity do not produce fluid interface expansion). The Darcy's differential equations presented in equation (1) can be modified now by the level set function to indicate whether or not the region is filled by the fluid according to

$$H(\phi) \nabla\left(\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \cdot \nabla p\right) = \frac{-\partial V_f / \partial p}{V_f} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

where $H(\phi)$ is a step shape function depending on the level set function local value. Typically, this function is smoothed-out in a narrow transition region of the fluid front in order to avoid numerical problems during the integration of the equations. For those regions filled by the fluid ($\phi < 0$), the step function acquires the value of the unity being zero in the unfilled regions ($\phi > 0$).

The coupled system of the Darcy's and level set update equations, (3) and (2) respectively, was solved within the 2D domain corresponding to the laminate rectangle shape $L \times B$ using the finite differences method, Figure 3. The spatial domain is discretized using a uniform grid (i,j) with equally spaced increments Δx and Δy . The first and second order spatial derivatives arising from the Darcy's equation are approximated with the central differences scheme being the time derivative in the same equation discretized with an standard forward Euler method using Δt as time increment. According to Osher and Sethian [5], the best way to solve the hyperbolic level set equation (2) is by a combination of the forward Euler scheme for the time discretization and the upwind spatial algorithm for the spatial framework.

Figure 3. Infused bag and sketch of the finite differences discretization of the infused domain.

4 RESULTS

The model described above was programmed in Matlab and applied to simulate the infusion experiments described in the previous sections [4]. The material properties, fluid viscosity, fabric permeability volume fraction dependence $K = K(V_f)$ and fiber bed compressibility $V_f(p_{\text{fiber}})$ were determined independently from experimental tests. A uniform grid with $\Delta x = 3.125\text{mm}$ and $\Delta y = 2\text{mm}$ was used to capture the evolution of the flow front during the experiments. The time increment was set to $\Delta t = 0.01\text{s}$ to ensure the Courant CFL condition was fulfilled during the whole analysis. The model was run in two steps. First, the inlet pressure was exponentially raised up and maintained constant through the filling stage up to $t \approx 8000\text{s}$. After that point, the inlet was closed (prescribing zero fluid velocity -or zero partial derivative of the fluid pressure- to those points of the grid belonging to the inlet) and this second post-filling stage is maintained up to the end of the experiments at $t \approx 10000\text{s}$.

The comparison between experiments and simulation results of the evolution of the compaction displacement during the infusion experiment for the $[0]_8$ and $[0]_4$ laminates is presented in Figure 4. The compaction displacements were obtained with the fabric stress using the Terzaghi's effective stress equation with the fluid pressure computed with the model which allowed the determination of the variation of the reinforcement volume fraction (or thickness variation). The agreement between the numerical results and the experiments is good in average in terms of time evolution and magnitude of the fabric compaction. Some discrepancies arise at the flow front position during the saturation of the fabric although the general trend of the experiments is adequately captured by the model. The thickness change recorded with the digital image correlation system experiences an initial decrease due to fiber-to-fiber contact lubrication and a subsequent thickening due to the stress transfer between the infused fluid and the fiber bed. In this case, the lubrication effect was not taken into account in the fiber bed compressibility curve and the simulation results were not able to capture such phenomenon. After the flow front reach an specific position, the fluid pressure builds up and the atmospheric pressure is shared with the fiber bed resulting in the corresponding thickness increase. The agreement is also good during the post-filling phase when the inlet gate is closed and the fluid pressure inside the bag is homogenized until a steady-state regime is attained.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A level set based model was developed to study the effects of flow and fabric compaction during vacuum infusion of composite materials. The level set approach is an excellent tool to handle problems with moving boundaries as in the case of injection/infusion problems where the materials state changes from dry to wet. Mathematically, a level set function (with the zero level corresponding to the flow front) is introduced in the Darcy's-continuity equations separating the different regions of the material. Additionally, a hyperbolic equation for the evolution of the level set function is introduced in the model. The partial derivative equations resulting from the problem are discretized and solved approximately using the finite differences method with a uniform grid discretization of the spatial domain. The time derivatives of the level set equation are approximated with the forward Euler method while the upwind algorithm is used for the spatial framework which take into account the hyperbolic nature of the evolution equation. For the Darcy's continuity equation, a standard Euler

method for time and central differences algorithm for the spatial derivatives are used. The level set is initialized to the distance function to the inlet gate and this function evolves according to the differential equations during the infusion time. However, after some time extent, the level set function is not longer the distance function and some reinitialization algorithms should be applied in order to maintain the accuracy of the solution.

A set of detailed of uniaxial flow infusion experiments with corn syrup mixtures through an $[0]_8$ and $[0]_4$ E-glass plain woven preforms were carried out in order to understand the compaction phenomena. The digital image correlation system was used to account for the deformations induced by the stress transfer between the fiber preform and the infused fluid. The system used a set of images acquired during the experiments which allowed to approximate the three dimensional displacement field of the vacuum bag, and therefore, the fabric compaction displacement. The digital image correlation was demonstrated to be a robust non-contact measurement system to measure compaction displacement of the vacuum bag surface with a good accuracy level. Moreover, the system allowed to track the flow front assuming that the fabric saturation takes place when its thickness started to grow as a consequence of the stress transfer from the infused fluid. This approximation was demonstrated to be accurate enough and do not require to have a direct optical access to the flow front which could be potentially interesting when dealing with infusion through carbon preforms. The material parameters used in the model, viscosity, in-plane permeability and fiber bed compaction were determined from independent tests. Specifically, the in-plane permeability and the fiber bed compaction dependence with the fabric volume fraction is taken into account through specific constitutive equations. The results of the model were compared with the infusion experiments and the general agreement is fairly good in terms of fabric compaction displacement and fluid pressure fields and filling times.

Figure 4. Comparison between experimental and simulation results: a) Displacement evolution at 11, 32, 50, 70 and 90% of the infusion length of a $[0]_4$ laminate, b) Displacement evolution at 11, 32, 50, 70 and 90% of the infusion length of a $[0]_8$ laminate.

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